

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

The Starry Night (1889) - Vincent van Gogh

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Ab initio

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Page Three Astronomy

Uranian System

image 5.1'x3.1' @ LRO
stack 493x2sG400
midpt 6:40:29 pm,
19 Dec 2025 Eastern
OTA: 190mm Orion RC
cam: QHY174M-GPS
planet disc center:
RA 03 42 58.6,
Dec 19 30 21
dist 18.634 AU
c/o Dr. Ted Barnes

Mags:

Uranus	5.86
Titania	13.82
Umbriel	14.90
Oberon	14.03
Ariel	14.25
Miranda	16.20
(obscured by disc)	

Stars show g-mags

The Uranian System

This is an ideal planet-and-moons system for the astronomy student. Something very exciting happened to Uranus early in its history; it is unique in having a system of moons that orbit approximately perpendicular to the ecliptic. Instead of appearing in a line, the Uranian moons can be seen executing nearly circular orbits around the planet. Following the moons in these orbits could be an interesting exercise. A telescope of at least 6" to 8" aperture would likely be required for this project.

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Secretary, IT: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

ORION Speaker POC: Richard Piety

Member w/o Portfolio: Art Allison

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

The TRAPEZIUM reports on events sponsored by the ORION Astronomical Society, including the Monthly Meeting in Oak Ridge, Public Stargaze events held twice monthly at TAO, and additional activities such as "Dark Stargaze" nights for observing notable events of special interest to our astronomers and astrophotographers, and Meteor Showers and Moongazes of interest to the general community. The Trapezium also provides a forum for the publication of astronomical material contributed by ORION members, such as astrophotography and reports of the results of astronomical research carried out at TAO such as asteroid occultations, lunar phenomena, observations of comets, and other curious things.

Messages from ORION

President's Message

- Don Spong

It was nice to see a good attendance at our 3rd annual Orion Festival of the Winter Solstice and Christmas Dinner on Friday, December 12. Also, there were many tasty potluck contributions; thanks for the cooking contributions and for the work of the organizers. Although I've been out of town since December 18, I don't think we've had many Tamke-Allan Stargazes to talk about. The cold weather seems to have shut things down for awhile.

January 3 was the full moon (known as the Wolf Moon) and the new moon will be on January 29, with January 17 and 18 a good dark sky weekend. A variety of planets are now visible, including Neptune, Saturn, Jupiter and Uranus. As the month goes on we will lose access to Saturn, as it will begin to set too early in the evening. Jupiter will be in good position. January meteor showers include the Quadrantids, but this has already happened, on January 2. We've had a nice selection of comets over the past few months, including the mysterious 3I/Atlas. However, most of them are leaving our neighborhood now, so there are not many new targets coming up. Comet 24P/Schaumasse can be seen with a 6" or larger scope in the early morning. A variety of deep space objects are in good viewing position for January. Starting first with the star clusters, we have: M45 (the Pleiades) in Taurus, M15 in Pegasus, NGC 869 and 884 (the Double Cluster in Perseus). Nebulae include: M42 (the Orion Nebula) in Orion, NGC2237/C49 (the Rosette Nebula) in Monoceros, IC410/NGC1893 (Tadpole) in Auriga, IC1848/IC1805 (Soul/Heart) in Cassiopeia, NGC1499 (California) in Perseus, M76 (Little Dumbbell) in Perseus, and the Bubble Nebula in Cassiopeia. Galaxies include: M31 (the Andromeda Galaxy) in Andromeda, NGC 891/C23 (the Outer Limits Galaxy) in Andromeda, and M33 (the Pinwheel Galaxy) in Triangulum. Another interesting object is Sharpless 136 (the Ghost Nebula) in Cepheus, comprised of wispy molecular clouds; this is near the Iris Nebula. So, get out and observe/image, but dress warmly!

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way :

David Fields

January 2026

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for Roane State's Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO). Traveling West on Caney Creek Road from Roane County Park, the sign appears on the left just after crossing Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month, weather permitting. For the winter, gates open at 7:00 pm and we continue until nominally 10:30 pm, or later when the sky and attendance are encouraging. Our Stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

Join us on Saturday Jan. 17 and Feb. 7, weather permitting, at TAO for our Stargazes. We also support the International Friendship Bell Stargaze in Oak Ridge, expected on a clear 1st Quarter Moon evening between Jan. 23 and Jan. 27.

This month's IFB Stargaze will be held in Bissel Park, Oak Ridge.

The event (discussion, bell ringing, viewing) begins at 7 pm on a scheduled evening, with the larger scopes positioned in the parking area just South of the bell. The parking area overlooks the bell, and is more friendly to people with heavy telescopes who like to observe beside their car. It's a short walk across the bridge up to the telescope overlook.

Observatory Way (cont.)

Our December Festival of the Winter Solstice and Christmas Party

We had a happy crowd of about 35-40 people, enjoying tasty food, astrophotos, and music. The conversation was great.

Thanks to David Allred for his help in hosting our big group and for taking some photos to share! Thanks also to High Places Community Church for the support it gives to our community!

Thanks to Don Spong for bringing his computer and sharing some of his and Ted Barnes' excellent astrophotos, and to Jim Long for bringing along Marvin the Martian.

Several of the active TAO astronomers received RSCC pins from the college in appreciation for their contributions at our Public Stargazes.

Thanks to the folks who shared food, and those who stayed and helped with washup and cleanup.

We've many other nice photos of the event, and have included them in another Trapezium article, "ORION Last Month," so have a look there!

Observatory Way (cont.)

Changes at TAO

We're always improving our presentations and projects (asteroid occultations, lunar meteor impact, equipment improvements, class support, etc.). The latest (thanks to Richard Piety) is an outdoor visitor greeting / registration station just outside the classroom door. We hope to add additional signage to help our visitors find their way around our campus after dark.

Lunar Impact Flashes and Asteroid Occultations

We've had several successful observation sessions the past month, primarily by Richard Piety, Ted Barnes and Don Spong. Ted has done a lot of nice analysis of the occultation data, while Rob Fowler has made great progress in the automated processing of Lunar Videos to detect the lunar flashes from impacting meteorites.

These projects are summarized elsewhere in the Trapezium – have a look!

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler. This set closes out the entries for 2025, and begins those for 2026.

Stardate: 2025.12.08

In attendance were Richard Piety, Art Alison, Don Spong, Ted Barnes, David Fields and Rob Fowler.

- Richard suggested we need additional signage and lights to guide guests to the classroom.
- We discussed the Winter Festival start time, officially 6pm so we are arriving at 5:30pm. We discussed how many attendees there may be.
- David located a new parking area nearer to the Friendship bell that will be better for in-town star gazes.
- David asked if anyone has a 4x4 foot piece of plywood to build a ramp for the telescope barn to facilitate rolling telescopes out.
- Robert reported on alternatives to zoom and whether we should switch to youtube or continue paying for zoom.
- Afterwards we resumed talking about signage and the need for better signage and reflectors.

Stardate: 2025.12.15

In attendance were Dave Fields, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- It was generally agreed that the holiday party was a big success, with about 40 in attendance. We agreed that next year we should have a planning committee.
- David mentioned that we are considering new projects for 2026.
- Richard discussed results from the new LIF project. There were difficulties in submitting his data due to a server problem. Thus far he has identified no new LIFs.
- We discussed not yet having a speaker for January. David shared contact info for a few more potential speakers.
- Richard suggested having a TAO cookout in August to coincide with the Perseid Meteor shower. Possibly 11-13 August, weather permitting.

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.12.22

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Richard Piety and Robert Fowler, and visitor John Rather.

- Richard suggested we need additional signage and lights to guide guests to the classroom.
- Ted announced that a French researcher from L'observatoire du Paris is interested in Richard Piety's recent occultation data.
- Rob discussed his plan for detecting events in LIF data.
- David discussed ongoing issues with the TAO Meade LX-200 mount and optical path.

Potential projects discussed for 2026 include:

- Adding HDMI wiring between the telescopes and the classroom. We decided to investigate a wireless method instead.
- Being able to live stream from TAO.
- Increasing bandwidth at TAO, and adding an additional classroom display for a telescope feed.

Stardate: 2025.12.29

In attendance were Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- We discussed the results of attempting to process LIF data.
- Richard attempted to record an occultation on 12.27, by asteroid 35988.
- Richard expressed frustration that the old facebook page needs to point people towards the new facebook group.
- We also discussed the need to keep presentations short at TAO.
- David Fields arrived at 2:45pm and observed and admired Ted's Xmas present, "Starry Starry Cat," a van Gogh style t-shirt.

This concludes the report of topics discussed at the ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito in 2025.

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito: 2026 - Rob Fowler

This compilation, which will be added to in subsequent issues, will present the topics discussed and any decisions made at the ORION Board Meetings held at the El Cantarito Mexican Restaurant in Oak Ridge, TN in Anno 2026.

Stardate: 2026.01.05

In attendance were Ted Barnes, Richard Piety, David Fields and Robert Fowler, with visitor John Rather.

- Richard discussed upcoming January occultations.
- Robert briefly discussed the LIF data analysis software he is developing.
- Ted discussed recent issues with his CGX telescope mount tracking. He believes that changing an RA backlash setting in CPWI may have improved it.
- David brought up the idea of establishing an Astronomy Society at Roane State.
- He also discussed a potential student project at TAO, possibly a model of Stonehenge.
- Noah confirmed by phone that he is this month's ORION Speaker.
- Re signage at TAO; Ted has acquired an arrow sign from Home Depot to direct visitor traffic.

ORION Monthly Meetings

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a holiday dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: How the upcoming Nancy Grace Roman Telescope compares to the Hubble and James Webb Space Telescopes

Speaker: Noah Frere

M.S., Astrophysics

U.Tenn. / Knoxville

Knoxville Bonsai Society, VP

Abstract:

The Hubble showed us images of nebulae that changed the public's perception of space altogether. It was a groundbreaking telescope that affected the very Zeitgeist. The JWST (James Webb Space Telescope), though incredible, did not seem to quite have that effect, much like the discovery of Eris, while a game-changer, lacked the power to inspire the population in the same way that the discovery of Pluto had, three quarters of a century earlier. The Nancy Grace Roman Telescope, set to launch in 2027, is a complement to the two aforementioned telescopes, with a resolution similar to Hubble but on a grand scale, thus offering insight into science objectives that the other two scopes cannot access. I will compare the technology and abilities of these three wonderful space telescopes.

Bio:

Noah Frere is primarily an astrologer, offering private consultations, in order to align one's soul to the divine order, chaos, and workings of the cosmos. He also tunes and repairs pianos, is a crossing guard, and teaches Astronomy at Roane State College and Indiana University as an Adjunct. He believes in the separate modalities of science as well as spiritual techniques, while also enjoying how they blend and interweave.

ORION Last Month – 12 Dec 2025

3rd Annual ORION
FESTIVAL of the
WINTER SOLSTICE
& Christmas Dinner

In keeping with tradition we held our 3rd Annual ORION Winter Solstice Festival at the High Places Community Church, Grove Center in Oak Ridge, with an additional mention of Christmas and Dinner this year, to hopefully draw in more attendees. This seems to have been a success, as we had an estimated 30 to 40 people present. Several pictures of the celebrants follow. We hope to see you again next year!

FESTIVAL of the WINTER SOLSTICE & Christmas Dinner

[Meal Planning](#) [Recipes](#) [Send Them A Meal](#) [Newsletter](#) [Help](#) [Contact Us](#)

You're Invited! **ORION Festival of the 2025 Winter Solstice and Christmas** (Fri, December 12, 2025 ... 6 pm, eat soon)

Meal Coordinator: [The ORION Board](#) 865 498 9319

Meal Location: [Historic Grove Theater \(High Places Community Church\), Grove Center, Oak Ridge, TN 37830](#) [\[view map\]](#)

Notes from the ORION Board ...

ORION's FESTIVAL of the WINTER SOLSTICE and Christmas Dinner will be a potluck: Opening at 6pm, dine soon after!

We encourage attendees to wear something in the spirit of the holidays. We invite you to bring your own utensils, cups, plates and napkins. Please review the food items list at the link below, and choose something you would like to bring to share with the group. Choose whatever appears needed, and fills in the gaps.

If you bring additional friends and family members, please list another item or items that you plan to bring. (Perhaps something for each attendee.)

6:00 pm: Arrive and set up

6:30 pm: Start of the dinner

8:30 pm: Cleanup; let's leave it beautiful for the next celebration.

We hope to see you at the Historic Grove Theater on Friday Dec.12 evening!

Signup link: <https://www.perfectpotluck.com/meals.php?t=RGLT4470>

ORION Last Month (cont.)

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Events, Calendars, and Sky Map

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2026

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2026 we plan to hold fixed-calendar Public Stargaze events on most of the 1st and 3rd Saturdays of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). A “Lepro LE” 5-mode red and white light rechargeable model is available from Amazon for about \$10 (Dec. 2025), and is a personal favorite. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged until everyone is packing up at the end of the event. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline. And PLEASE NO CAR HEADLIGHTS ON SITE!*

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to both bring and consume coffee and other refreshments.

(v. 14 Jan 2026)

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2026

In 2026 we plan to continue our schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site ORIONastronomy @ groups.io.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours of approximately 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm, with some variation.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline. A right arrow at the entrance to the TAO grounds shows visitors the direction to their preferred parking area.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page, and in several pages following.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2026; Jan & Feb 2026

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2026 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for six month periods, currently Jan-Jul 2026. This appears on the page immediately following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent two months appear after the six-month “Public Stargaze” calendar(s).

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as <http://www.roanestate.edu/obs> before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jan-Jun 2026

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 03 Jan 2026	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 17 Jan 2026	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 07 Feb 2026	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 21 Feb 2026	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 07 Mar 2026	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 21 Mar 2026	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 04 Apr 2026	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 18 Apr 2026	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 02 May 2026	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 16 May 2026	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 06 Jun 2026	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 20 Jun 2026	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

These 2026 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAO Calendar Special Events (all times Eastern)

Jan 2026

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 03 Jan 2026		Full Moon 05:03 am Eastern		
Sat 03 Jan 2026	cancelled 	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Mon 12 Jan 2026		Dark Stargaze Two Occultations	ca. 5:00 pm	midnight
Sat 17 Jan 2026		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sun 18 Jan 2026		New Moon 12:52 pm Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events (all times Eastern)

Feb 2026

date	event	details	start	end
Sun 01 Feb 2026		Full Moon 05:09 pm Eastern		
Sat 07 Feb 2026		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sun 17 Feb 2026		New Moon 07:01 am Eastern		
Sat 21 Feb 2026		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm

TAO Public Stargazes in January and February:

Sat 17 Jan 2026

Sat 17 Jan 2026

Sunset	5:51 pm
Civ dusk	6:19 pm
Ast dusk	7:01 pm
Moonrise	7:13 am
Moonset	4:43 pm

Moon illum. 1%

**Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.**

Sat 07 & 21 Feb 2026

Sat 07 Feb 2026

Sunset	6:13 pm
Civ dusk	6:40 pm
Ast dusk	7:40 pm
Moonrise*	12:22 am
Moonset*	10:51 am
	*08 Feb

Moon illum. 68%

**Waning Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon very late in this event.**

Sat 21 Feb 2026

Sunset	6:27 pm
Civ dusk	6:53 pm
Ast dusk	7:53 pm
Moonrise	9:19 am
Moonset	11:16 pm

Moon illum. 19%

**Waxing Crescent Moon.
Crescent Moon visible during this event.**

TAO Calendars

2025 retrospective

Jan-Jun & Jul-Dec 2025; Nov & Dec 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for six month periods, currently Jul-Dec 2025. These appear on the two pages immediately following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations**, **Meteor Showers**, **Full Moonrises**, **Lunar (and other) Eclipses**, **Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the two six-month “Public Stargaze” calendars.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

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TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

2025 Retrospective

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Public Stargaze

Jul-Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Jul 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 02 Aug 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 16 Aug 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sun 07 Sep 2025	<small>moved</small> ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 04 Oct 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Oct 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Mon 03 Nov 2025	<small>moved</small> ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 06 Dec 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 20 Dec 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm

2025 Retrospective

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events (all times Eastern)

Nov 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 01 Nov 2025	★	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sun 02 Nov 2025	⊕	End of DST 2025		1:00 am
Wed 05 Nov 2025	○	Full Moon 08:19 am Eastern		
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Thu 20 Nov 2025	●	New Moon 01:47 am Eastern		

2025 Retrospective

date	event	details	start	end
Thu 04 Dec 2025		Full Moon 06:14 pm Eastern		
Sat 06 Dec 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm
Fri 12 Dec 2025		ORION Winter Solstice & Christmas Dinner Festival	6:00 pm	t.b.a.
Fri-Mon 12-15 Dec 2025		Lunar Impact Flash (LIF) Campaign	00:49 am 12 Dec 2025	06:09 am 15 Dec 2025
Fri 19 Dec 2025		New Moon 08:43 pm Eastern		
Sat 20 Dec 2025	cancelled 	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm

2025 Retrospective

The evening Sky Map for January 2026 from skymaps.com.

The Evening Sky Map

FREE* EACH MONTH FOR YOU TO EXPLORE, LEARN & ENJOY THE NIGHT SKY

Sky Calendar - January 2026

Follow on Bluesky
skymaps.com/blsky/

- 1 Moon at perigee (closest to Earth) at 21:39 UT (distance 360,348km; angular size 33.2').
- 3 Full Moon at 10:03 UT.
- 3 Earth at Perihelion (closest to Sun) at 17h UT. The Sun-Earth distance is 0.983302 a.u. (147.1 million kilometers).
- 3 Quadrantid Meteor Shower peaks at 21h UT. Active between December 28 and January 12. Expect up to 25 meteors per hour under dark skies. Radiant is in northern Boötes. Northern hemisphere only. Moonlight interferes.
- 4 Moon near Jupiter at 0h UT (morning sky). Mag. -2.7.
- 6 Venus at superior conjunction with the Sun at 16h UT (not visible). The brightest planet passes into the evening sky.
- 6 Moon near Regulus at 18h UT (morning sky).
- 9 Mars at conjunction with the Sun at 12h UT. Mars passes into the morning sky.
- 10 Jupiter at opposition at 9h UT. This is the best time to view the largest planet in the Solar System. Mag. -2.7.
- 10 Last Quarter Moon at 15:48 UT.
- 11 Moon near Spica at 0h UT (morning sky).
- 13 Moon at apogee (farthest from Earth) at 21h UT (distance 405,438km; angular size 29.5').
- 14 Moon near Antares at 21h UT (morning sky).
- 18 New Moon at 19:52 UT. Start of lunation 1275.
- 21 Mercury at superior conjunction with the Sun at 16h UT (not visible). The innermost planet passes into the evening sky.
- 23 Moon near Saturn at 10h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.2.
- 26 First Quarter Moon at 4:47 UT.
- 27 Moon near the Pleiades at 22h UT (evening sky).
- 29 Moon at perigee (closest to Earth) at 21:46 UT (distance 365,871km; angular size 32.7').
- 31 Moon near Jupiter at 4h UT (evening sky). Mag. -2.6.

More sky events and links at <http://Skymaps.com/skycalendar/>
 All times in Universal Time (UT). (USA Eastern Standard Time = UT - 5 hours.)

★ Support The Evening Sky Map ★
 • Helping curious minds to explore the night sky since January 2000 •
 Recommended Products for Sky Watchers: skymaps.com/store/
 All sales support the production of this free resource. Thank you.

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE JANUARY 2026

SKY MAP SHOWS HOW THE NIGHT SKY LOOKS
 EARLY JAN 8 PM
 LATE JAN 7 PM

SKY MAP DRAWN FOR A LATITUDE OF 40° NORTH AND IS SUITABLE FOR LATITUDES UP TO 85° NORTH OR SOUTH OF THIS

THE SKY MAP IS THE PART OF THE SKY DIRECTLY OVERHEAD THE OBSERVER'S HEAD. THE HORIZON LINE IS THE PART OF THE SKY WHICH IS ON THE HORIZON. THE CENTER OF THE MAP IS THE CENTER OF THE MAP. THE CENTER OF THE MAP IS THE CENTER OF THE MAP.

Star Magnitudes ● -1 0 1 2 3 4
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 * TERMS OF USE: FREE FOR NON-COMMERCIAL EDUCATIONAL USE. ASTRONOMY EDUCATION GROUPS MAY FREELY DISTRIBUTE PRINTED HANDOUTS. FULL DETAILS AT <http://skymaps.com/terms.html>

Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

The evening Sky Map for January 2026 from skymaps.com.

About the Celestial Objects

Listed on this page are several of the brighter, more interesting celestial objects visible in the evening sky this month (refer to the monthly sky map). The objects are grouped into three categories. Those that can be easily seen with the naked eye (that is, without optical aid), those easily seen with binoculars, and those requiring a telescope to be appreciated. **Note, all of the objects (except single stars) will appear more impressive when viewed through a telescope or very large binoculars.** They are grouped in this way to highlight objects that can be seen using the optical equipment that may be available to the star gazer.

Tips for Observing the Night Sky

When observing the night sky, and in particular deep-sky objects such as star clusters, nebulae, and galaxies, it's always best to observe from a dark location. Avoid direct light from street lights and other sources. If possible observe from a dark location away from the light pollution that surrounds many of today's large cities.

You will see more stars after your eyes adapt to the darkness—usually about 10 to 20 minutes after you go outside. Also, if you need to use a torch to view the sky map, cover the light bulb with red cellophane. This will preserve your dark vision.

Finally, even though the Moon is one of the most stunning objects to view through a telescope, its light is so bright that it brightens the sky and makes many of the fainter objects very difficult to see. So try to observe the evening sky on moonless nights around either New Moon or Last Quarter.

Astronomical Glossary

Conjunction – An alignment of two celestial bodies such that they present the least angular separation as viewed from Earth.

Constellation – A defined area of the sky containing a star pattern.

Diffuse Nebula – A cloud of gas illuminated by nearby stars.

Double Star – Two stars that appear close to each other in the sky; either linked by gravity so that they orbit each other (binary star) or lying at different distances from Earth (optical double). Apparent separation of stars is given in seconds of arc (").

Ecliptic – The path of the Sun's center on the celestial sphere as seen from Earth.

Elongation – The angular separation of two celestial bodies. For Mercury and Venus the greatest elongation occurs when they are at their most angular distance from the Sun as viewed from Earth.

Galaxy – A mass of up to several billion stars held together by gravity.

Globular Star Cluster – A ball-shaped group of several thousand old stars.

Light Year (ly) – The distance a beam of light travels at 300,000 km/sec in one year.

Magnitude – The brightness of a celestial object as it appears in the sky.

Open Star Cluster – A group of tens or hundreds of relatively young stars.

Opposition – When a celestial body is opposite the Sun in the sky.

Planetary Nebula – The remnants of a shell of gas blown off by a star.

Universal Time (UT) – A time system used by astronomers. Also known as Greenwich Mean Time. USA Eastern Standard Time (for example, New York) is 5 hours behind UT.

Variable Star – A star that changes brightness over a period of time.

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE
JANUARY 2026

CELESTIAL OBJECTS

Skymaps.com

Easily Seen with the Naked Eye

- Capella Aur • The 6th brightest star. Appears yellowish in color. Spectroscopic binary. Dist=42 ly.
- Sirius CMa • The brightest star in the sky. Also known as the "Dog Star". Dist=8.6 ly.
- Procyon CMi • Greek name meaning "before the dog" – rises before Sirius (northern latitudes). Dist=11.4 ly.
- δ Cephei Cep • Cepheid prototype. Mag varies between 3.5 & 4.4 over 5.366 days. Mag 6 companion.
- Deneb Cyg • Brightest star in Cygnus. One of the greatest known supergiants. Dist=1,400 ±200 ly.
- Castor Gem • Multiple star system with 6 components. 3 stars visible in telescope. Dist=52 ly.
- Pollux Gem • With Castor, the twin sons of Leda in classical mythology. Dist=34 ly.
- Vega Lyr • The 5th brightest star in the sky. A blue-white star. Dist=25.0 ly.
- Rigel Ori • The brightest star in Orion. Blue supergiant star with mag 7 companion. Dist=770 ly.
- Betelgeuse Ori • One of the largest red supergiant stars known. Diameter=300 times that of Sun. Dist=430 ly.
- Aigol Per • Famous eclipsing binary star. Magnitude varies between 2.1 & 3.4 over 2.867 days.
- Pleiades Tau • The Seven Sisters. Spectacular cluster. Many more stars visible in binoculars. Dist=399 ly.
- Hyades Tau • Large V-shaped star cluster. Binoculars reveal many more stars. Dist=152 ly.
- Aldebaran Tau • Brightest star in Taurus. It is not associated with the Hyades star cluster. Dist=66.7 ly.
- Polaris UMi • The North Pole Star. A telescope reveals an unrelated mag 8 companion star. Dist=433 ly.

Easily Seen with Binoculars

- M31 And • The Andromeda Galaxy. Most distant object visible to naked eye. Dist=2.5 million ly.
- M2 Aqr • Resembles a fuzzy star in binoculars.
- M38 Aur • Stars appear arranged in "pi" or cross shape. Dist=4,300 ly.
- M36 Aur • About half size of M38. Located in rich Milky Way star field. Dist=4,100 ly.
- M37 Aur • Very fine star cluster. Discovered by Messier in 1764. Dist=4,400 ly.
- M44 Cnc • Praesepe or Beehive Cluster. Visible to the naked eye. Dist=590 ±200 ly.
- M41 CMa • First recorded observation by Aristotle in 325 BC as "cloudy spot". Dist=2,300 ly.
- μ Cephei Cep • Herschel's Garnet Star. One of the reddest stars. Mag 3.4 to 5.1 over 730 days.
- Mira Cyt • Famous long period variable star. Mag varies between 3.0 & 10.1 over 332 days.
- χ Cygni Cyg • Long period pulsating red giant. Magnitude varies between 3.3 & 14.2 over 407 days.
- M39 Cyg • May be visible to the naked eye under good conditions. Dist=900 ly.
- ν Draconis Dra • Wide pair of white stars. One of the finest binocular pairs in the sky. Dist=100 ly.
- M35 Gem • Fine open cluster located near foot of the twin Castor. Dist=2,800 ly.
- γ Leporis Lep • Visible with binoculars. Gold & white stars. Mags 3.6 & 6.2. Dist=30 ly. Sep=96.3".
- R Lyrae Lyr • Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.9 & 5.0 over 46.0 days.
- 2232 Mon • A large scattered star cluster of 20 stars. Dist=1,300 ly.
- 2244 Mon • Surrounded by the rather faint Rosette Nebula. Dist=5,540 ly.
- M50 Mon • Visible with binoculars. Telescope reveals individual stars. Dist=3,000 ly.
- Cr 69 Ori • Lambda Orionis Cluster. Dist=1,630 ly.
- M42 Ori • The Great Orion Nebula. Spectacular bright nebula. Best in telescope. Dist=1,300 light years.
- M15 Peg • Only globular known to contain a planetary nebula (Mag 14, d=1"). Dist=30,000 ly.
- Double Cluster Per • Double Cluster in Perseus. NGC 869 & 884. Excellent in binoculars. Dist=7,300 ly.
- 253 Scl • Fine, large, cigar-shaped galaxy. Requires dark sky. Member of Sculptor Group.
- Mizar & Alcor UMa • Good eyesight or binoculars reveals 2 stars. Not a binary. Mizar has a mag 4 companion.

Telescopic Objects

- γ Andromedae And • Attractive double star. Bright orange star with mag 5 blue companion. Sep=9.8".
- γ Arietis Ari • Impressive looking double blue-white star. Visible in a small telescope. Sep=7.8".
- M67 Cnc • Contains 500+ stars mag 10 & fainter. One of the oldest clusters. Dist=2,350 ly.
- η Cassiopeiae Cas • Yellow star mag 3.4 & orange star mag 7.5. Dist=19 ly. Orbit=480 years. Sep=12".
- 61 Cygni Cyg • Attractive double star. Mags 5.2 & 6.1 orange dwarfs. Dist=11.4 ly. Sep=28.4".
- γ Delphini Del • Appear yellow & white. Mags 4.3 & 5.2. Dist=100 ly. Struve 2725 double in same field.
- β Eridani Eri • Striking blue-white double star. Mags 3.2 & 4.3. Visible in a small telescope. Sep=8.2".
- β Monocerotis Mon • Triple star. Mags 4.6, 5.0 & 5.4. Requires telescope to view arc-shape. Sep=7.3".
- Mon Ori • Christmas Tree Cluster. Associated with the Cone Nebula. Dist=2,450 ly.
- Orion Ori • Superb multiple star. 2 mag 7 stars one side, mag 9 star on other. Struve 761 triple in field.
- Tau Ori • Crab Nebula. Remnant from supernova which was visible in 1054. Dist=6,500 ly.
- Tri Tri • Fine face-on spiral galaxy. Requires a large aperture telescope. Dist=2.3 million ly.
- M81 UMa • Beautiful spiral galaxy visible with binoculars. Easy to see in a telescope.
- M82 UMa • Close to M81 but much fainter and smaller.

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Observing Reports

Observing Lunar Impact Flashes: My Experience

- Richard Piety

The Geminid Observing Campaign was organized to evaluate the use of citizen scientists for detecting and verifying the impacts of meteorites on the lunar surface. This project was organized by multiple institutions in support of the ESA (European Space Agency) funded LUMIO Mission (Lunar Meteoroids Impact Observer). ESA is due to launch the LUMIO CubeSat mission in 2028.

The institutional contacts for this effort include:

- Detlef Koschny / Technical University of Munich (TUM)
- Tony Cook / University of Aberystwyth
- Elisa Maria Alessi / Institute of Applied Mathematics and Information Technologies (IMATI_CNR)

The web site for more information is <https://lif.mi.imati.cnr.it/> . The User Group is lunar-impacts@groups.io.

The goal is to record flashes of light resulting from meteor impacts on the non-sunlit portion of the lunar surface that is visible from earth. To be most effective data is typically acquired before the first quarter or after the third quarter to maximize the lunar area under observation.

The Geminid Campaign was designed to take advantage of the likelihood of meteoroids related to the Geminid Meteor Shower increasing the probability of impacts. The target days included Dec 12, 13, and 14. The analysis of the overall project is on-going and will be left to the principal investigators to summarize and report. But I will give a brief overview of my experience.

As luck and Tennessee weather would have it, Dec 12 and Dec 14 were overcast, and I was unable to acquire any data on those dates. I did succeed in capturing 2.5 hours of data during an interval of increasing cloudiness beginning at 03:30:00 EST on Dec 13.

The equipment consisted of a Celestron C8 SCT with a Celestron .63 focal reducer and QHY174M-GPS camera, riding on an ZWO AM5 mount. I captured the data onto a Windows 11 laptop computer running Stellarium 25.2 and SharpCap 4.1 software.

Lunar Impact Flashes (cont.)

After polar aligning the scope, I repositioned the scope on the moon. I adjusted focus, then played with the camera's region of interest (ROI) settings and position until I could cover the majority of the non-sunlit portion. The camera's final settings were 1920x1068 ROI, MONO8, 50 msec frames, and SER video format. I prefer the SER format for the ease of recovering frame-by-frame time stamps, which I rely on so heavily when recording asteroid occultations.

Due to the needs of the Automatic Lunar Flash Investigation (ALFI) software provided for analysis, I recorded the data in 10 minute segments. Each 10 minute video required 23.8 GB of storage and contained almost 12,000 frames.

The sky was looking reasonably clear as I started to set up my equipment but by the time the moon had risen above the nearby trees I could see waves of haze moving across the image. This haze got increasingly thick until by the end, I frequently lost all visibility and I finally gave up around 6 am EST.

I spent several hours converting files and analyzing data, but all candidate flashes reported by ALFI appeared to be false positives. Even with the clouds I could see stars appearing from behind the moon that I identified as being mag 10. I was hopeful that any LIF of at least that magnitude would still be detectable.

To rule out false positives, the general practice is to verify a LIF by having a second observer from some distance away also see the LIF. There was one potential LIF reported during my observation window. When I went back to the video and checked, there was a flash in my data in the same general region of the moon at the same reported time. This LIF was prominent in one frame and faded over the next two frames. It looks like the real deal! It was also something the ALFI software completely missed.

Upon finding this I sent in a report to the Collaboration confirming the LIF. It does make me wonder if there are others that ALFI missed, but with 110,000 frames I won't be looking at every frame manually!

Lunar Impact Flashes (cont.)

Fig.1 Before LIF.

Fig.2 LIF detected.

Lunar Impact Flashes (cont.)

Fig.3 LIF fading (frame translated to the right).

Fig.4 On video, LIF barely detectable. Not really seen here.

Lunar Impact Flashes (cont.)

Fig.5 Post LIF

A couple of weeks ago, Richard Piety mentioned that he was having a problem with the LIF Project (Lunar Impact Flashes) and the programs provided by that group. He had tried to analyze some of his files looking for potential LIFs and found mostly random noise, in the form of lots of false hits. But what wasn't detected in all those hundreds of false hits was an actual LIF that he found when someone called him and asked him to confirm one they had found. Naturally that was a mystery. Why would programs capable of detecting hundreds or even thousands of false hits, miss a valid one? If the settings are sensitive enough to catch a lot of false detections, it seems only logical that would flag an actual hit.

This peaked my curiosity, and Ted Barnes suggested "Maybe you would like to look into this?" He was right. The thing about programming as a hobby is that you seldom come across an interesting project. So it didn't take much encouragement to get me interested, especially after Richard showed us the sample data he found, data that looked like an actual hit but was not detected by the existing software. There was plenty of contrast. It wasn't like you could miss it. But with hundreds of thousands of frames to review, the software must work. There is no logical way to review them all by hand. So how did the software miss it? Intriguing!

I expressed an interest, and Richard sent me a batch of ten frames that included the one frame that shows what looked like an actual Lunar Impact Flash. All I had to do was write the code to detect it.

If you have never coded in BASIC, image files can be tricky because there is so much you have to handle. It's more than just knowing how many pixels are on a line. Most image file formats include some form of compression. And decoding that can become a whole world unto itself. You have to deal with that before you can even begin to concern yourself with width and height and color depth. BUT these were bitmaps. A standard bitmap (.bmp files) uses no compression. So if you already know the number of pixels on a line and you know how many lines there are, you are ready to open a bitmap.

LIF Analysis Programs (cont.)

```
5 ' GLOBALS
6 Const GRIDW = 32
7 Const GRIDH = 32
8
9 Dim Shared imgW&, imgH&, frameCount&
10 Dim Shared grid(GRIDW - 1, GRIDH - 1)
11 Dim Shared cellW!, cellH!
12 Dim Shared dragging%, dragStartX!, d
13
14 ' MAIN PROGRAM
15
16 Dim serFile$, serPath$, serName$
17
18 serFile$ = _OpenFileDialog$("select a
19
20 If serFile$ = "" Then
21     Print "No file selected."
22 End If
23
24 ' Extract path and filename
25 serPath$ = Left$(serFile$, _InStrRev(se
26 serName$ = Mid$(serFile$, _InStrRev(se
27
28 Call LoadSERHeader(serFile$, imgW&, im
29
30 If headerOK% = 0 Then
31     Print "Invalid or unsupported SER f
32 End If
33
34 Screen _NewImage(imgW&, imgH&, 32)
35
36 Ask user which frame to load
37 Dim frame$
38 Dim frameNum&
39
40 Print "This SER file contains"; frameCou
41 Print "Enter frame number to load (1 to"
42 Print frameNum&
43
44 Convert to 0-based index
45 frameNum& = frameNum& - 1
46
47 If frameNum& < 0 Or frameNum& >= frameCou
48 Print "Invalid frame number."
49 End If
50
51 Load the selected frame
52 frame$ = LoadSERFrame$(serFile$, frameSize
53
54 Convert MONO8 to displayable image
55 DrawFrame(frame$)
56
57 Compute grid cell size
58 ! = imgW& / GRIDW
59 ! = imgH& / GRIDH
60
61 ... - click here or ctrl+... to ...
```

An example of a code snippet written in QB-64, Phoenix Edition.

LIF Analysis Programs (cont.)

Technical mumbo-jumbo: The type of bitmaps we are concerned with here are 8-bit greyscale, since that is what the image capture program SharpCap produces under the name “MONO8.” These files begin with a 54-byte “metadata” header that contains information about the number of pixels per line, the number of lines, and the color depth. We already know we are dealing with 8-bit greyscale files. That implies that one byte describes one pixel. The value of that byte is interpreted as brightness. After the header, the 55th byte is the first pixel on the left of the bottom line of the image. And as we proceed deeper into the file we move down the line from left to right. Then, with no breaks, the next line of data is the image line one step above the previous image line. So the data is actually encoded upside down in a bitmap file. I have been assured by competent engineers that back when windows was in its infancy, there was a logical reason for this. The only departure from this pattern is when the image line length is not evenly divisible by 4. In those cases, the line is padded out to become evenly divisible by 4. That’s it, that’s the whole mystery. At least for 8-bit greyscale images.

On my first attempt at an image analysis program I decided to partition the bitmap into smaller zones, determine an average brightness for each zone, and then flag anything that was significantly brighter than the average. But I soon realized this would be a mistake because an actual hit (a big area) could raise the average brightness of the zone enough that the hit might go undetected. Subsequently I explored the idea of checking each pixel against the same pixel in the previous frame. As I was detecting lots of random hot pixels, I tried tweaking certain numbers that controlled the detection threshold. This worked well in theory. So I next tried running large sets of thousands of files. I noticed while running through one very large batch of frames that it found many random hits in the first 6200 frames, and then found nothing in the remaining 11k frames. That seemed very unlikely; noise shouldn’t just go away like that. Initially I assumed I had a bug in my program that causing it to stop looking for new hits, but none was found. Eventually, I realized that the gap in finding new hits was due to changing conditions, such as “no clouds” transitioning to “thin clouds” or “fog.”

LIF Analysis Programs (cont.)

Then it dawned on me that I may have just exposed the fatal flaw of the program provided by the LIF project. If you run the first hundred frames and tweak the settings perfectly for those frames, conditions may change causing those settings to be useless later on. I decided that I needed an automatic way to set the threshold independently for every frame. And although it slows the program down a fair amount, it now produces much better results. And it easily detects the LIF in Richard's data.

I asked Richard and Ted for some sample data to test my programs. And I soon realized the value of something Richard said. The frame can only include whatever portion of the moon is in shadow, as including the daylight portion created thousands of false hits. However, it's not always practical to keep the daylight out of the image entirely. So, it becomes necessary to be able to mask out portions of the image, effectively telling my program "Don't look here." For instance, if the daylight rim of the moon is visible on the left, you need to create a bitmap mask with black there to mask out that region. The program will then only look for LIFs in the image data where it sees a specific shade of white in the mask.

As of this writing, Richard is testing my programs by processing his data, and providing feedback about what works well and what doesn't. If we achieve positive results that are better than those produced by the LIF team's software, we will offer these programs to the LIF team for their future analysis runs. Stay Tuned!

LIF Analysis Programs (cont.)

LIF Review Program (c/o RF) showing a lunar impact in Richard Piety's data.

December Occultations: (2745) San Martin and (445) Edna.

- Richard Piety

There were two asteroid occultations I had the opportunity to capture during December:

- **(2745) San Martin** occulting UCAC4 441-046379 at UT 03:41:16 Dec 20, and
- **(445) Edna** occulting UCAC4 601-036226 at UT 03:16:59 Dec 31.

I was using my standard setup for occultations; a Celestron C8 with Hyperstar v4, and a QHY174M-GPS camera mounted on a ZWO AM5 mount. Also, a Win 11 laptop running Stellarium 25.2 and SharpCap 4.1. Data was recorded as SER format video in MONO16. After analysis with PyMovie/PyOTE reports were generated and sent to the International Occultation Timing Association (IOTA).

The (2745) San Martin occultation became challenging as it only cleared the nearby trees about 15 minutes before the main event. Enough clouds and haze came in that I had to increase from the planned <100 msec exposure to 300 msec. Increasing the gain with the cloud reflectivity only made things worse, and I still ended up at a gain of 400. As I was capturing the data the haze thinned, but too late to change my exposure time. Even with the haze I still got reasonably solid data.

The event duration was at a maximum of 1.0 sec and I was only 1 mile from the shadow centerline. I prefer to have a minimum of 6 data points within an occultation. The 300 msec wouldn't give me the desired number of data points, but not being visible wouldn't give me anything.

On the last (UT) day of 2025 I collected data on (445) Edna occulting a mag 13.0 star. This was another Tennessee evening with a passing cloudy haze. Since the occultation duration was 5.9 secs and I was less than a third of the shadow distance out from the centerline, I used 500 msec frames with a camera gain of 350 on this dim star in poor seeing. During moments of better seeing I could see the asteroid as it approached the target star, as they were close to the same magnitude. (See my images from before and after the occultation.)

See the data plot and summary on the following pages for the results. Unfortunately, due to the fluctuating conditions the data quality is rather poor. This occultation had several other stations monitoring it, including 8 positives.

December Occultations (cont.)

(2745) San Martin: Occultation 20251220

December Occultations (cont.)

(445) Edna: Occultation 20251231

December Occultations (cont.)

The blue arrow indicates the approaching asteroid (445) Edna;
the red arrow indicates the mag 13 Target Star

Post Occultation

Occ by a rock: 2745 San Martin (Fri 19 Dec 2025)

- Ted Barnes

Another late December occultation that drew the attention of our local group was by the asteroid 2745 San Martin. In reading through an online discussion between asteroid occultation experts from the IOTA organization I learned that the recent increase in the rates of reporting occultation events has become a problem for the organization, and they are beginning to encourage observers to concentrate on specific types of occultations. Campaigns by groups of observers are encouraged, as those can be used to generate approximate

profiles of the asteroids involved. Of the more traditional timed observations that observers record in which the occulted “target star” disappears and reappears, known as “single-chord observations,” the events that are now considered the most important are those involving smaller asteroids, of the few km scale. This is because there are many more such objects, and their orbits are usually much more poorly known than those of the larger asteroids (such as those with diameters on the 10 to 100 km scale). And the smaller asteroids above about 5 km in diameter are considered potential “planet killers,” so their orbits are certainly of interest to the local sentient inhabitants. For some reason I think of these now favored several-km diameter asteroids as “rocks.”

One such rock, 2745 San Martin, would be occulting a star in late Dec 2025, and this event would be visible in East Tennessee. 2745 San Martin is an Inner Main Belt asteroid (semimajor axis only 2.289 AU) and a member of the Phocaea group. Like many of the smaller asteroids it has a rather large orbital inclination ($i = 22.41$ [deg]) and a largish eccentricity of $e = 0.1894$. According to the JPL Horizons database, 2745 San Martin has a diameter of 5.2(2) km, only about 3 miles. At the time of the occultation it would be at mag 15.9. For those who are curious, a JPL Horizons orbit diagram for 2745 San Martin is shown on the following page.

A small asteroid casts a similarly small shadow, so not many observers would be in a position (inside the shadow) to record this occultation. The program Occult Watcher, which gives detailed information regarding future occultations, noted that 2745 San Martin would be occulting the star UCAC4 441-046379 at about 10:41:15 pm Eastern on 19 Dec 2025. Although this event would not be visible at TAO, it would be visible both

**Tue 19 Dec 2025
Oak Ridge, Tenn.**

Sunset	5:27 pm
Civ dusk	5:55 pm
Ast dusk	6:59 pm
Moonrise	7:38 am
Moonset	4:54 pm

Moon illum. 0%

New Moon.

No Moon visible during this event.

Occ by a rock: 2745 San Martin (cont.)

from my home observatory LRO and from Richard Piety's home site PHO. Our two sites were coincidentally on almost the same chord, so similar durations were expected; the durations measured the travel time of the target star's image behind the asteroid, and the paths it followed would be quite similar. And as our sites were separated by 7.35 km, it was anticipated that the observed disappearance and reappearance times would differ by about a half second, since a typical occultation shadow velocity is about 15 km/sec. (Note to self: figure this out.)

A JPL Horizons orbit diagram for asteroid 2745 San Martin at the time of the occultation, 10:41 pm Eastern 19 Dec 2025, at a distance of 1.052 AU from Earth.

In preparing to observe this occultation at home (LRO) I noticed a difficulty; the event would take place at the terrestrial coordinates **Alt@Azi = 17.9°@106.3°**, rather low in the East in Hydra, near the border with Monoceros. This Azimuth was near a low location in my treeline, and when I had last measured the treeline (21 Aug 2022) it reached a low point at 12°@104°, and rose slightly to about 15°@106°. So, although this event was near the 2022 treeline, I should clear it by approximately 3°. I was careful to move the mount to “stage left” in LRO, where I had a clear view of that low point.

Occ by a rock: 2745 San Martin (cont.)

Alas a new check of the treeline showed that the trees had been growing rapidly in the anomalously hot and wet climate of our new carbon burning era, and the low point in the treeline was now up to about $18^\circ@104^\circ$, and reached about 19.5° at 106° . So, the 2745 San Martin occultation would actually take place about **2° below** the treeline.

This was a potential disaster. I had prepared for this event by capturing SER movie files of test fields near Alhena, with stars of magnitudes near the target star's g-mag of 11.9, using 200ms frames and a gain of 480. This had worked quite well down to star mags of 13.0, but these test images were of course captured *above* the tree line. Although one can occasionally capture images through trees, and essentially all the leaves had now fallen, I would now be imaging through many small tree branches. With an expected maximum duration of only 1.0 sec it didn't seem realistic to increase the frame length much beyond 200 ms, although I probably should have. At the time I decided to image as planned, and hope for the best.

At least the local field (shown below) was characteristic. To the right of the field a triangle of 12th mag stars was visible, and the target star was at the bottom left of that triangle. The field was framed by a "bright" 9.5 mag star at far left, and at bottom a fainter 10.0 mag star with an 11.3 mag companion. According to TheSkyX the stars in the small triangle at right were, moving clockwise from top, mags 12.2, 11.7, and (target star) 12.3.

Orion8"RC + QHY174M, GPS + 75% photoreducer

The local starfield near 2745 San Martin at the time of the occultation.

Occ by a rock: 2745 San Martin (cont.)

To show the difficulty of imaging through the branches, here we show an enhanced image of the same local field, in a much longer 1000msG480 single exposure, captured about 6.5 mins after the event, at 10:47:40 pm Eastern. All the stars with given magnitudes in the field on the previous page here can readily be identified, but this is 5x the frame exposure time used in the SER movie.

Imaging through tree branches: The local starfield of the previous page in a single 1.0 sec exposure (1sG480), about 6 mins after the occultation.

Although the target star is clear in the 1.0 sec frame shown above despite the tree branches, identifying it **reliably** in the SER movie was much more difficult. The 1.7 GB SER movie I captured is a set of 750 200msG480 MONO8 frames, full-field (1920x1200 px) from StartCapture 10:41:07.5645 pm Eastern to EndCapture 10:42:37.6074 pm. (Times are from the SharpCap log, rounded to 4 digits after the decimal.) I attempted to process the SER file using Pymovie, but the images of the 12th mag triangle of stars were too indistinct to discern. I was instead reduced to a frame-by-frame examination of the file using the SER Player viewer. Setting both the gain and gamma to max (3.0), I was almost always able to see the 11.3 mag star at bottom, and usually able to see the 12th mag triangle, although it went through indistinct periods. Since I knew the predicted event time

Occ by a rock: 2745 San Martin (cont.)

10:41:15 pm Eastern, I started about two seconds earlier with frame 328, timestamped (UT) 03:41:12.9832, and assessed visibility of the stars in the 12th mag triangle through frame 353. The target star, **12.3**, is in boldface. My results were as follows (rounding 12.9832 to the midpoint 13.1, and stepping by 0.2 secs (+ = visible, blank = not visible):

<u>Frame</u>	<u>Midtime</u>	<u>11.3</u>	<u>12.2</u>	<u>11.7</u>	<u>12.3</u>
328	13.1	+	+	+	+
329	13.3	+	+	+	+
330	13.5	+	+		+
331	13.7	+	+	+	+
332	13.9	+	+	+	
333	14.1	+	+	+	+
334	14.3	+	+	+	
335	14.5	+	+	+	+
336	14.7	+		+	+
337	14.9	+			+
338	15.1	+	+		+
339	15.3	+	+	+	+
340	15.5	+	+	+	+
341	15.7	+	+	+	+
342	15.9	+	+	+	+
343	16.1	+	+		
344	16.3	+		+	
345	16.5	+	+	+	
346	16.7	+	+		
347	16.9	+	+	+	+
348	17.1	+	+		+
349	17.3	+	+	+	+
350	17.5	+	+	+	+
351	17.7	+	+	+	+
352	17.9	+	+	+	+
353	18.1	+	+	+	+

The problem here is that flickering is evident in the 12th magnitude stars, so in the 12.3 mag target star we cannot be certain when it is actually occulted versus when it is not clear due to atmospheric effects. Subject to these uncertainties, our table is consistent with the target star being occulted for about a second, centered on 10:41:16.4 pm Eastern. Frames from before, during and after are shown on the next page.

Occ by a rock: 2745 San Martin (cont.)

Here we show crops of the 12th mag triangle of stars, from equally spaced frames 341, 344 and 347, respectively before, during and after the presumed occultation. The target star is at bottom left. These were edited for enhanced brightness and contrast. No attempt was made to align these images precisely. The times are Eastern midpoints, rounded as described on the previous page.

frame 341
10:41:15.5

frame 344
10:41:16.1

frame 347
10:41:16.7

Based on this rather weak data and the other frames in the SER movie, a report was submitted to IOTA on 26 Dec 2025 stating that we had evidence for an observation of the occultation by 2745 San Martin at LRO, times (UT) 03:41:15.9(1)-16.8(1) 20 Dec 2025, duration 0.9(1) [sec]. It was noted that this was consistent with the observation (with clearer data) by R. Piety, with the same duration but 0.8 [sec] after his observation, about as expected given the different locations of the two observing sites.

Clearly it will be interesting in future to compare the timing differences observed between these sites for a given occultation, which are in principal known accurately from the predicted shadow velocity and direction of travel.

The Last Occultation of 2025: 445 Edna (30 Dec 2025)

- Ted Barnes

Our local group of serious asteroid occultationists frequently check the tabular format output of the program Occult Watcher, “OW,” for new events that may prove attractive. Often it isn’t clear in retrospect who first noticed that a given interesting occultation was approaching. This was the case with 445 Edna; it was very close to the end of the year, between Christmas and New Year’s, which sounded like an amusing time to catch a final 2025 occultation. The most interesting aspect of this event was just how many other observers had

“signed on” in OW as planning to attempt to capture this event. Usually one sees at most just a few names, if any, but for 445 Edna the number of planned observers rose to something like 15 just before the event. Was something special afoot, such as a campaign to assemble a network of observers who could produce an outline of the asteroid? In the IOTA online discussion group I have since asked why 445 Edna was so popular, but thus far no one has responded.

In any case 445 Edna did appear at least somewhat attractive; the time of the predicted occultation was unusually convenient, 10:17 pm Eastern. Other attractions were a long duration (max 5.9 seconds), and a position well above the horizon, Alt@Azi = 59°@90°, in the constellation Gemini. Although TAO was closed due to very cold weather, at my home observatory LRO this was in the relatively small range of azimuth in which I did not encounter trees. The rather steep altitude angle of 59° did require that I move my telescope mount forward and partially outside, to clear the low roof projection, which was inconvenient but not impossible. (I did have to readjust the mount tripod to compensate for a rapid downward slope outside the doorway.) Other difficulties included a bright gibbous Moon with 80% illumination, only separated from the occultation by 46°. In addition the target star was rather faint, at a g-mag of only 13.0; that combined with the bright moonlight might make this a difficult occultation to record after all. Since 445 Edna at mag 13.5 was comparable to the target star, one could expect to see both near the time of the occultation. Their combined magnitude would be about 12.5. In view of the bright Moon and relatively faint target star, I decided to be cautious and use long 500 ms frames at the maximum camera gain, 480. A large scale view of the sky at the time of the event, generated by TheSkyX, is shown on the following page. The brightest nonlunar object in this sky by far was the planet Jupiter, also in Gemini, at magnitude -2.7.

Tue 30 Dec 2025

Sunset	5:33 pm
Civ dusk	6:02 pm
Ast dusk	7:05 pm
Moonrise	1:50 pm
Moonset*	4:52 am
	*31 Dec

Moon illum. 80%

Waxing Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon visible during this event.

The Occultation of 445 Edna (cont).

The asteroid 445 Edna in Gemini at the time of the occultation, 10:16:59 pm Eastern, 30 Dec 2025. Image generated using TheSkyX. Here for emphasis we show a few interesting asteroids as small red dots. •

The Occultation of 445 Edna (cont).

A JPL Horizons orbit diagram for asteroid 445 Edna, a Tholen type C (carbonaceous) asteroid in the Outer Main Belt, with a diameter of about 90 [km]. This shows its position at the time of the occultation, at a distance of 2.038 AU from Earth.

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

Since TAO was closed, Richard Piety planned to record this occultation from his home site, PHO. I accordingly decided to try to capture it from my home site LRO, near Clinton, 6.35 km distant from PHO. As mentioned above I am graced by an overabundance of trees, and am on the West side of Lost Ridge, so my only useful view is to the East. This is discussed in more detail in the preceding report on attempting to observe 2745 San Martin 11 days earlier. In the case of 445 Edna the occultation was high in the East, so the trees were not a problem.

A few days earlier I had asked Rob Fowler if he would like to visit LRO and participate in this event, and he replied that he was indeed interested if the weather was cooperative. So, during the afternoon of 19 Dec I prepared by moving the mount tripod into the panel door opening of the “LRO observatory building” (garage), levelled it to within about an 0.3% slope, rearranged my computer and monitor table to be close enough to the mount for operations (the high speed USB 3.0 camera cable is not long), and tested the Celestron CGX mount control program CPWI. On slewing the mount to $\text{Alt@Azi} = 59^\circ@90^\circ$ I was surprised to see just how steep this appeared to be, and how close the f.o.v. seemed to approach the edge of the roof. As it would have been a major effort to move the setup further outside, I decided to use this configuration and hope for the best.

LRO, 19 Dec 2025, 4:44 pm Eastern. Testing the CGX mount at $\text{Alt@Azi} = 59^\circ@90^\circ$, to capture the occultation by 445 Edna. As you can see this is quite steep! (The OTA is not yet mounted.) The gps antenna is under an unused oil funnel, well why not?

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

Once Rob arrived and it was dark enough (Civil Dusk began at an early 6:02 pm) I began aligning the system. In using CPWI one can choose between 1) setting up a new alignment, or 2) resynchronizing on a single star, using an earlier, saved alignment set of sufficient quality. The latter always sounds more attractive, and is usually a mistake, since it assumes that the mount has not been moved since that earlier alignment set was saved. So, I tried using an earlier set, the reckless option 2. After some time it was clear that this was problematic, because a new saved star when rechecked after a slew was no longer accurately in the saved position. I kept adding new stars and rechecking, but the positions were simply not being saved properly. And most disturbing, a long slew (I think from Jupiter to Procyon) resulted in the cursor indicating the OTA's position jumping during transit. Rob's theory of this crazy behavior was that by using SharpCap's Align and Resync Tool during alignment I may have saved contradictory star positions that resulted in very inaccurate slews. In any case, several attempts at starting from scratch were equally unsuccessful. This was a disaster. Without an accurate alignment it was simply not possible to slew to the position of the occultation.

Solving this alignment problem seemed less critical once the weather turned. I should mention that the predicted weather for this 445 Edna event at LRO had been discouraging for days, with several services predicting 100% overcast locally at the time of the occultation. As 30 Dec had proven to be surprisingly clear and sunny through sunset, I was hoping that the forecasters just had it wrong, which happens not infrequently. However the CSC predictions included two different cloud developments, a Canadian one predicting mostly clear evening skies, and a new European one showing much thicker clouds through early evening. By 8 pm those much thicker clouds had abruptly arrived with a vengeance, and we had a nearly complete overcast. That, we said with some amusement and perhaps relief, was the end of Edna.

Clearly we should go back inside the house where it was warm, and watch Star Trek (on daily from 8 pm through 1 am over the air from a sympathetic Crossville station). From inside I could check my office computer monitors for any sign of improving skies from a much warmer setting. It was an especially bad episode of TOS, and then about 9:30 pm during TNG, an hour before the occultation, I noticed that my office monitor now showed a clear sky through the guide scope! We went outside and saw that a large region of the Eastern sky was indeed clear. Was there a chance for this occultation after all? Unfortunately we still had the unsolved alignment problem to address, with only about an hour to go.

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

I should also mention that it was now very cold outside, close to freezing. Clear thinking and a determined calm resolve are alas not traits that cold weather brings out in me. Rob suggested that since we couldn't align the system, but SC's plate-solve tool (without resync) was working well, perhaps we could repeatedly do short, roughly directed slews followed by plate solves, since we knew the desired final coordinates. That seemed sensible, especially since 445 Edna was in Gemini, and we were already in Gemini. So, I looked up the occultation's coordinates, and we did short hops and repeatedly used plate solving to test our progress. This and using the schematic CPWI star map seemed to work, and we were soon in the right general area. Next we watched the OTA's star field on the monitor as I did short slews in various directions. Suddenly I recognized the three bright stars in the lower left of the target field (see below, image generated using TheSkyX). We had done instrument flying, and had now reached our destination! As it was just now 10 pm, we only had to stay on that field, with a clear sky (please), for 15 more minutes.

Alas guiding wasn't working, but tracking was ok, and we only had a problem of stars slowly drifting upwards, which I corrected with short slews every few minutes.

Below: The expected OTA field of 445 Edna at 10:16:59 pm Eastern; note the three bright stars at lower left.
Image generated using TheSkyX.

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

I did capture a quick image of the converging pair of 445 Edna and the target star, UCAC4 601-036226, which is shown below. The target star is g-mag 13.0, and appears to be a spectral type F giant, at 4.3(3) [kpc]. This image is a 500ms single exposure at gain 480, to test how clearly these objects would be recorded in a SER movie with 500msG480 frames. This image was moderately enhanced in contrast. The ASPS plate solver gives an image center of RA 06 44 37 and Dec +30 09 22, with an image scale of 0.949 [asecs] per pixel. The fitted camera angle was found to be a slightly rotated $\theta_{\text{Cam}} = 2.96$ [deg] (the image below is counterrotated accordingly), and the fitted focal length was 1273 [mm].

Below: A 500msG480 single frame image of the predicted occultation location, taken at 10:00:07 pm Eastern, according to the gps timestamp at image upper left. Compare with the expected field shown on the previous page; the agreement is excellent. The slightly fainter asteroid 445 Edna at mag 13.5 is just to the left of the g-mag 13.0 target star. The position of 445 Edna, as determined by plate solving this image using ASPS, agrees with the prediction of the JPL Horizons Ephemeris for this time to within about 0.2'' in RA.

2025 12 31 03:00:07.0618812 Z

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

Finally, this is an enlarged and contrast-enhanced crop from the ASPS plate solver image from near the center of the image on the previous page. This shows the target star and approaching asteroid when they were separated by about 11.6 [asecs] (according to JPL Horizons, using their Ephemeris for 445 Edna.). A careful counting of pixels in the figure shows that the separation between the asteroid and target star in the image below is about 11-12 px. Since the plate solver finds that $1 \text{ px} = 0.95 \text{ [asec]}$ in this image, that corresponds to a separation of about 11 [asec], consistent with the JPL separation.

It was possible to distinguish the asteroid and target star as separate objects until about 5 minutes before the occultation, corresponding to a separation of about 3 [asec].

The asteroid and target star at 10:00:07 pm Eastern, 30 Dec 2025.
Observed separation *ca.* 11 [asec]. This image is 4.4 x 2.9 [amin].

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

The SER movie file of the occultation, consisting of 250 frames of 500 ms duration at a gain of 480 (250x500msG480), was captured without difficulty, with the SC log recording a start time of 10:16:00.6535 Eastern, and a finish time of 10:18:05.6668. A Pymovie plot of the observed luminosity in 3 apertures, the target star (blue points), a comparison star (green points), and an empty region (no star, red points) is shown below. The x-axis shows frame number, running from Pymovie number 0-249. Points are separated by 500 ms. The location of the occultation event is very clear.

The manner in which the target (blue) and comparison (green) stars show a closely correlated, somewhat irregular modulation over time scales of ~ 10s of secs outside of the event region shows that there was an atmospheric dimming effect.

A Pymovie display of the luminosity observed in three different apertures of the 250-frame SER movie file. The start and finish times are approximately 10:16:00.7 – 10:18:05.7 pm Eastern, 30 Dec 2025. The occultation is evident just left of middle.

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

The PyOTE square well fit to the target star luminosity in the 250-frame SER movie file. The resulting fitted occultation parameters are given on the following page.

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

The recorded luminosity at three apertures of the SER movie file and the PyOTE square well fit are shown on the previous two pages.

Analyzing the SER file using the programs Pymovie and PyOTE gave disappearance and reappearance times (UT, 31 Dec 2025) D and R with 1σ errors of

$$D = 03:16:55.33(10)$$

$$R = 03:17:00.40(10)$$

and an event midpoint time of

$$T_{\text{midpt}} = 03:16:57.86(7) .$$

This midpoint compares well with the predicted midpoint of 03:16:58, which included an estimated error of 0.4 [sec].

Our result for the duration (from PyOTE, with 1σ errors), is

$$\text{dur} = R - D = 5.08(15) \text{ [sec]}.$$

In comparison, the predicted maximum duration was 5.9 [sec].

The observed magnitude drop during an occultation often provides an important check of the accuracy of the measurement. With 1σ errors we observed (from Pyote)

$$\text{magDrop} = 0.86(4) \text{ [mag]}$$

which is consistent with the predicted value of 0.83 [mag].

PyOTE's version of a S/N ration, which they call the DNR, was 3.40 in this analysis.

The Last Occultation of 2025 (cont).

In summary, despite the chaos of the initial system alignment effort, and the overcast weather earlier in the evening, we were able to observe and record the occultation by 445 Edna of the target star UCAC4 601-036226 successfully, and analyses of this data using the Pymovie and PyOTE programs gave interesting results, of greater accuracy than the predictions published earlier.

Of the 12 sites that had announced planned observations of this event, 8 reported successful events. All but one was on the “right side” of the asteroid’s profile, and the occultation durations reported to OW (which quotes them to at most 0.1 [sec] precision) ranged from 4.2 to 5.3 [sec]. Our number of 5.1 [sec] (at this precision), at a distance of 20.6 [km] from centerline, was bracketed by 5.2 [sec] at 20.1 [km] and 4.7 [sec] at 25.2 [km]. No inconsistencies were evident.

We note in passing that Richard Piety also observed this occultation from his station PHO in Powell, TN, and reported a disappearance time of 10:16:55.4(2) Eastern, and a duration of 5.0(4) [sec]. These numbers are not distinguishable from our results given the errors. Although one would normally expect to observe a difference in event timings between LRO and PHO due to the 6.4 [km] separation between these sites, in this case the shadow edge was moving approximately perpendicular to their separation vector, so the difference in event times was considerably reduced. It appears that PHO was leading by about 2 [km] along the shadow path, so the PHO times should lead the LRO times by about 0.1 [sec]. This difference is smaller than our reported errors, and so could not be resolved in this occultation. Similar comparisons would be interesting in future, and with three local sites providing accurate timings it should be possible to determine both the velocity and angle of advance of the asteroid shadow’s edge.

Lessons learned at LRO from this event were that a new telescope mount position should be tested for slewing problems beforehand, especially for an event at a high altitude. Probably doing a new alignment before the actual night of the observation is advisable as well. Reusing an earlier alignment set from a different mount position is *not* advisable. Another lesson learned, yet again, is to take weather predictions *cum grano salis*. At least in East Tennessee, one should establish the local weather conditions during the event through frequent personal observations. I’m from Missouri.

Astrophotography

M42, IC 1805 and IC 63

- Don Spong

As mentioned last month, I've recently added a new telescope (a Stellarvue SVA130EDT-R refractor) to my arsenal. I had just one night in December to get out and try it out. Below is my first image with this telescope of the Orion nebula. While the imaging could have benefitted from longer exposure, I was pleased with the clarity and contrast of this initial try. I used my ZWO ASI533 camera and took 40 30-second exposures (gain of 100) that I stacked.

Oak Ridge, December 16, 2025

M42, IC 1805 and IC 63 (cont.)

From December 18 to January 7 I was visiting my daughter and family in San Francisco. Since their backyard is fairly dark and has a good view of the sky, I have stationed my smaller 72mm Apertura refractor and Skywatcher Star Adventurer GTI mount at their place, so that when traveling I can just bring a camera, tripod, ASI AIR, and guidescope to be set up to do some imaging. The following two images were captured using this setup (the camera was my ZWO 533). On the left is the Heart Nebula (IC 1805) a stack of 95 1-minute exposures. On the right is the Ghost of Cassiopeia (IC 63) a stack of 70 1-minute exposures. The bright star at right is Gamma Cassiopeia.

San Francisco, December 29, 2025

IC 1805

IC 63

Asteroid 4695 Mediolanum

- Ted Barnes

4695 Mediolanum is a small Middle Main Belt asteroid, diameter about 10 km. At the time of these images it was in the constellation Canis Minor, at an Earth distance of 1.362 AU, with a visual magnitude of 15.3. This asteroid was predicted to occult (eclipse) a faint 13.4 magnitude “target star,” UCAC4 461-036214, on Monday 12 Jan 2026, at a midpoint time of 9:39:03 pm Eastern. The event was expected to be visible from TAO, and was captured there by Richard Piety. These images show the asteroid shortly after that occultation.

Here we show three successive images of the asteroid at four-minute intervals as it departs the vicinity of the target star. Each image is a stack of 240 one-second frames, captured at my home observatory LRO near Clinton, which was outside the asteroid’s shadow. I used an ORION 8” Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph with a QHY174M-GPS camera at maximum gain and an 0.75x photoreducer. The image midpoints were 9:49:49, 9:53:49 and 9:57:49 pm Eastern.

The images shown below are cropped from extreme enlargements of the original stacks, to show the asteroid and target star clearly. Individual pixels are evident; each is 0.946 [asec] on a side. Of course there are quantum mechanical limits to the resolution that can be achieved; with “diffraction limited optics” one can resolve at best about 0.5 [asec] in a telescope with an 8” aperture. The actual objects span much smaller scales; the true asteroid image for example is expected to be about 10 [mas] in diameter, about 1/100 of a pixel. You would need a 20-meter aperture telescope to resolve an image at that tiny scale!

4695 Mediolanum departing the field of target star UCAC4 461-036214.

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc.
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺).

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$\text{Image scale [asec/px]} = 206.3 * \text{pixel size}[\mu\text{m}] / \text{focal length [mm]}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, with errors (from Gaia data, or Simbad if needed as an alternative).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.0054	41	Menkalinan	81.1	0.46
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6	7.0
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.0083	43	Alhena	109.3	8.2
4	Arcturus	36.72	0.22	44	Peacock	178.8	5.1
5	Vega	25.04	0.069	45	Alsephina	80.6	0.78
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7	16.4
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6	6.3
8	Procyon	11.46	0.051	48	Alphard	180.3	1.8
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8	0.33
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3	0.46
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	81.1	0.93
12	Altair	16.73	0.049	52	Nunki	227.8	4.6
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8	0.21
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0	1.01
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4	6.7
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6	0.77
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1	2.7
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9	0.63
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	974.	37.
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9	0.21
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	89.9	3.47
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0	4.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2	1.5
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6	18.0
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5	10.0
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	77.2	1.79
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5	85.
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1830	270
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3	0.7
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	231.5	8.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1080	40
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0	49.
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7	0.35
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.9	8.4
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6	11.
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5	27.
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2	66.
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7	0.27
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7	6.0
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	84.5	2.5

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		<u>Θ</u>	<u>$\Delta\theta$</u>	<u>defect (%)</u>
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

To The Moon

And, like a dying lady lean and pale,
Who totters forth, wrapp'd in a gauzy veil,
Out of her chamber, led by the insane
And feeble wanderings of her fading brain,
The moon arose up in the murky east,
A white and shapeless mass.

Art thou pale for weariness
Of climbing heaven and gazing on the earth,
Wandering companionless
Among the stars that have a different birth,
And ever changing, like a joyless eye
That finds no object worth its constancy?

Percy Bysshe Shelly (1792-1822)

Pub. 1824 by Mary Shelley, in "Posthumous Poems"

ORION and TAO Links and General Information

May be found at the following URLs:

ORION Astronomical Society
(general information and monthly calendar)
<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

ORION Facebook Group:
<https://www.facebook.com/share/g/1CP2Szq5ea/>

ORION online discussion group
ORIONastronomy@groups.io

TAO in Wikipedia
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

TAO access (incl. driving instructions)
<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

TAO Facebook Group:
<https://www.facebook.com/share/g/1BoDeViUjb/>

TAOCalendars for 2026:
pp. 23-27 of this issue

Where is TAO? (Bortle 5.0)

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854
Glow Dome = N 35° 49' 56.6", W 84° 37' 03.8"; Alt. 324 m
NE Pad = N 35° 49' 57.4", W 84° 37' 03.4"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook
N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m
Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)
N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

A full CERN zenodo doi url is for example <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253> ;
a short form, *e.g.* zenodo.org/records/8219253 may also be used.

Vol. 49, Issue 04; Fri 15 Apr 2023: zenodo.org/records/8219253

Vol. 49, Issue 05; Fri 12 May 2023: [8216818](https://zenodo.org/records/8216818)

Vol. 49, Issue 06; Fri 16 Jun 2023: [8030659](https://zenodo.org/records/8030659)

Vol. 49, Issue 07; Fri 14 Jul 2023: [8140396](https://zenodo.org/records/8140396)

Vol. 49, Issue 08; Fri 18 Aug 2023: [8251302](https://zenodo.org/records/8251302)

Vol. 49, Issue 09; Fri 15 Sep 2023: [8336647](https://zenodo.org/records/8336647)

Vol. 49, Issue 10; Fri 13 Oct 2023: [8433081](https://zenodo.org/records/8433081)

Vol. 49, Issue 11; Fri 17 Nov 2023: [10138151](https://zenodo.org/records/10138151)

Vol. 49, Issue 12; Fri 15 Dec 2023: [10382618](https://zenodo.org/records/10382618)

Vol. 50, Issue 01; Fri 12 Jan 2024: [10483283](https://zenodo.org/records/10483283)

Vol. 50, Issue 02; Fri 16 Feb 2024: [10672625](https://zenodo.org/records/10672625)

Vol. 50, Issue 03; Fri 15 Mar 2024: [10822600](https://zenodo.org/records/10822600)

Vol. 50, Issue 04; Fri 12 Apr 2024: [10967036](https://zenodo.org/records/10967036)

Vol. 50, Issue 05; Fri 10 May 2024: [11176951](https://zenodo.org/records/11176951)

Vol. 50, Issue 06; Fri 14 Jun 2024: [11646971](https://zenodo.org/records/11646971)

Vol. 50, Issue 07, Fri 12 Jul 2024: [12735071](https://zenodo.org/records/12735071)

Vol. 50, Issue 08, Fri 16 Aug 2024: [13333599](https://zenodo.org/records/13333599)

Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024: [13742825](https://zenodo.org/records/13742825)

Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024: [13921735](https://zenodo.org/records/13921735)

Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024: [14171218](https://zenodo.org/records/14171218)

Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024: [14394899](https://zenodo.org/records/14394899)

Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025: [14630165](https://zenodo.org/records/14630165)

Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025: [14873015](https://zenodo.org/records/14873015)

Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025: [15015954](https://zenodo.org/records/15015954)

Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025: [15200349](https://zenodo.org/records/15200349)

Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025: [15443035](https://zenodo.org/records/15443035)

Trapezium back issues online: (cont.)

Vol. 51, Issue 06, Fri 13 Jun 2025:	15660329
Vol. 51, Issue 07, Fri 11 Jul 2025:	15865574
Vol. 51, Issue 08; Fri 15 Aug 2025:	16884202
Vol. 51, Issue 09; Fri 12 Sep 2025:	17108361
Vol. 51, Issue 10; Fri 10 Oct 2025:	17316280
Vol. 51, Issue 11; Fri 14 Nov 2025:	17615148
Vol. 51, Issue 12; Fri 12 Dec 2025:	17873056
Vol. 52, Issue 01; Fri 16 Jan 2026:	18271961

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Acknowledgements:

References and credits to materials used to produce this issue are as follows:

This holiday season saw the appearance of a surprising number of images combining the ever popular topics of astronomy, van Gogh's art, and our feline friends. The best known of van Gogh's nighttime paintings is his "*Starry Night*" (June 1889), which is incorporated in the front cover of this issue.

A favorite of the Editor in this recent genre of wearable art-inspired images is a combination of two of van Gogh's images of the night sky, "*La Nuit étoilée*" (Arles, Sept. 1888) and "*Starry Night*" (June 1889), which shows an impression of the predawn Eastern sky in Saint-Rémy-de-Provence. This modern version, shown on the back cover, combines elements of both paintings with a black cat in the foreground (replacing a cypress in van Gogh's "*Starry Night*"). This kitty appears as fascinated by the night sky as we are. *n.b.* I have assumed that this beautiful image is not copyrighted, since the original paintings are in the public domain.

A sky chart for 445 Edna and local fields of view for the occultations by both 445 Edna and 1745 San Martin shown in this issue were generated by the Editor using the program TheSkyX.

The JPL Horizons database was used to generate orbit diagrams for asteroids 445 Edna and 2745 San Martin.

*Fin du journal.
Au revoir!*

